

Sharing the oxygen mask

Collaboration so we can all breathe more easily

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This contribution examined how third space practitioners can leverage individual expertise and collaboration to improve profile and impact. In this recorded session, we shared and discussed vignettes of practice, then demonstrated how to build greater visibility and recognition of the value of the third space. By using collaborative practice with other third space practitioners, we can create a stronger shared identity which gives us all a seat on the plane.

In this recording we provided an overview of a session that we presented recently at a UniSQ professional development day. Here we examined the third space in higher education to establish a shared understanding of the term and our current practice. We finished this presentation with vignettes of practice, that demonstrate how we have built greater visibility and recognition of the value of the third space. After watching the video, participants were invited to contribute to a Padlet.

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